

**Project Data Analytics Task Force
(PDATF)**

**Closing the Gap:
A Practical Framework for
Implementing Data Analytics
and AI into the Built
Environment**

GREEN PAPER
June 2025

Report Structure

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
POLICY & DELIVERY CONTEXT	5
THE OPPORTUNITY	7
BARRIERS	9
3.1 LEADERSHIP & ALIGNMENT	9
3.2 DATA POOLING & INTEROPERABILITY	10
3.3 DIGITAL & TECH CONSTRAINTS (INCLUDING LEGACY TECH)	11
3.4 SKILL AND CULTURE GAPS	13
3.5 PROCUREMENT & COMMERCIAL MODELS	14
3.6 RISK, ETHICS AND ASSURANCE	16
IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK	19
ROADMAP AND ROLES	21
POLICY LEVERS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	23
PRACTITIONER TOOLKIT (ANNEX)	24
CASE STUDIES	25

Executive Summary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data analytics have the potential to transform the delivery of major government projects and infrastructure—improving performance, increasing transparency, and enabling better outcomes for citizens. However, despite a raft of new

policies, government departments and their delivery partners continue to face systemic barriers that prevent AI and analytics theory from translating into real-world impact. Fragmented systems, legacy technology, siloed data, limited skills, and outdated procurement models are among the obstacles hindering progress.

This paper—*Closing the Gap: A Practical Framework for Implementing Data and AI into the Built Environment*—responds directly to these challenges by providing a structured framework and roadmap. It sets out target states for transformation in each barrier area, along with 90-day starter actions, 12-month milestones, and success metrics to evaluate progress and impact. The framework addresses six major blockers: leadership and alignment, data pooling and interoperability, digital and tech constraints, skill and culture gaps, procurement and commercial models, and assurance and ethics.

It is proposed that this Green Paper is updated to a White Paper over the coming months. The intention would be to further develop the content, make it more accessible to a non-technical audience, make the guidance more human rather than process centric and ensure that it will support professionals working in an often complex and messy context.

SIX MAJOR BLOCKERS:

Leadership & alignment

Data pooling and interoperability

Digital and tech constraints

Skill and culture gaps

Procurement and commercial models

To support implementation, we propose three headline recommendations:

1. Mandate project-level data strategies across all major programmes, aligned to IPA (now NISTA) and DSIT guidance, with funding and capability built in from the outset.
2. Establish a cross-government AI & Data Delivery Capability Hub, building on existing functions (e.g. NISTA, IPA, GDS), to support departments and delivery bodies with training, tools, and shared platforms.
3. Reform commercial and assurance processes to promote innovation and remove blockers to interoperability, ethical AI use, and outcomes-focused procurement.

This paper is intended as a bridge between policy and practice. Its goal is to equip delivery leaders, policymakers, and industry partners with the tools, clarity, and confidence to embed AI and data analytics at the heart of the UK's project delivery system—closing the gap between aspiration and execution. It aligns with the ambition set out in the UK Government's 10-Year Infrastructure Strategy (2025) [33], which identifies AI, data, and digital infrastructure as national enablers. PDA Taskforce analysis of the plan highlights major programmes—such as AI Growth Zones and the £2bn AI Opportunity Pipeline—that underscore the urgency for practical frameworks such as those proposed here.

Policy & Delivery Context

Over the past five years, the UK government has made significant progress in leveraging data and artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance public sector delivery. Key documents such as the [National Data Strategy \(2020\)](#) [28], the [UK National AI Strategy \(2021\)](#) [34], and the [Transforming Infrastructure Performance \(TIP\) Roadmap \(2021\)](#) [31] have laid the foundations for better data interoperability, stewardship and AI adoption. These strategies have set the stage for improved public outcomes

through digital transformation, predictive analytics, and AI-driven decision-making.

More recently, the government has taken steps to move from vision to execution. [The AI Opportunities Plan \(Department for Science, Innovation and Technology, 2025\)](#) [29] outlines 50 cross-sector actions to accelerate AI adoption, boost access to compute, and grow public sector capability. Supporting infrastructure such as the National Data Library and AI Growth Zones, and the

establishment of a dedicated AI Opportunities Unit, illustrate the operational commitment behind these ambitions. Further detail is provided in the forthcoming Infrastructure Strategy 10-Year Plan (2025) [33], which outlines investments across AI infrastructure, data centres, and defence digital capabilities. The PDA Taskforce reviewed these plans and noted the need for robust implementation structures. Many of the initiatives identified—such as AI Opportunity Zones and National AI Compute Infrastructure—lack any alignment with the key enablers such as interoperable standards, ethical assurance, and delivery-readiness.

The UK's AI and data strategy is robust, with key documents like the [AI Safety Institute's 2023](#) creation (renamed the [AI Security Institute in 2025](#)), updates to the [Magenta Book \(2024\)](#) and [Green Book \(2024\)](#) for AI and climate resilience, and

the recent [Teal Book \(2025\)](#) for managing infrastructure complexity. Despite these strong policy frameworks, practical implementation remains challenging due to fragmented systems, inconsistent data use, capability gaps, and siloed innovation, as highlighted in the [Project Delivery Functional Standard \(GovS 002\)](#) and the IPA [Project Delivery Data Strategy \(2022\)](#).

This paper responds directly to that implementation gap. It provides a practical, actionable framework to help government departments, and their delivery partners realise the benefits envisioned in national strategies. By addressing systemic enablers such as data interoperability, leadership alignment, digital readiness, procurement models, and assurance capability, it aims to move the conversation from policy ambition to on-the-ground transformation.

The Opportunity

The vital role of government project delivery in the UK's economic growth, infrastructure, services, and national security is clear. Projects are critical for sustaining economic recovery and meeting significant commitments like Net Zero by 2050. The Government Major Projects Portfolio alone represents substantial public expenditure and projected benefits. Leveraging data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is recognised as a clear opportunity to enhance government delivery and increase confidence in project outcomes. Using digital and data tools in the design, delivery, monitoring, and evaluation of major projects is identified as a way forward. Access to better data, analysis, and experience can drive continuous improvement.

However, significant challenges currently hinder realising these theoretical benefits, including increasing costs, tightening public spending, skills shortages, and particularly, data-related issues. Addressing data challenges involves improving the use of data in project controls, promoting predictive metrics and interactive data tools, establishing

Civil Servants

26,000

interoperable and reliable data and performance reporting, and enhancing data management and shared use.

The most substantial opportunity lies in addressing these critical data and AI barriers, alongside other challenges, collectively across the entire government system and with industry partners. The Government Project Delivery Function involves over 26,000 civil servants from diverse professions, working collaboratively with delivery partners from industry, professional bodies, and academia. Project delivery is fundamentally about people and partnership.

While the strategic case for embedding AI and data into project delivery is well established, operational uptake remains inconsistent. Structural challenges—spanning data architecture, digital infrastructure, procurement frameworks, organisational capabilities, and governance—continue to constrain progress. These barriers are not isolated but systemic, compounding one another across the project lifecycle. Without coordinated intervention, there is a risk that national ambitions set out in the AI Opportunities Plan, the National Data Strategy, and TIP will always remain nothing more than aspirational. The [10-Year Infrastructure Plan](#) [33] makes clear the government’s intention to mobilise over £2 billion in AI-enabled infrastructure initiatives. PDA commentary on the plan emphasises that this creates a generational opportunity to embed interoperable data standards, platform-based delivery, and assurance by design—if delivery mechanisms can be aligned to the ambition.

The following section identifies six critical barrier domains that must be addressed in tandem to enable scalable, trusted, and effective implementation across the built environment and government delivery ecosystem.

Barriers

Input to three barriers to unlock AI-enabled project delivery

The three barrier narratives express a common mutually reinforcing thread: **strategic alignment + capable people + modern commercial levers**. Tackling these in isolation invites “pockets of excellence”; addressing them together creates the ecosystem conditions in which trustworthy, scalable AI can flourish across UK project delivery.

3.1 Leadership & alignment

AI has reached a pivotal point for UK project delivery. C-suite conversations have shifted from *whether* to adopt AI to *how* to scale and gain value from it – yet evidence shows most programmes stall in the chasm between ‘proofs of concepts and pilots’ and ‘enterprise value from scaling’.

- Vision without business case.** Interviews with 44 senior infrastructure leaders found enthusiasm, but also “unclear return on investment (ROI), cultural resistance and siloed delivery models” cited as the dominant blockers to scale [1]. When capex-driven budgets meet AI’s opex-heavy pay-per-use costs, boards struggle to see the whole-life benefit story and therefore do not commit the necessary political capital and resources to gain the potential value.
- Fragmented governance.** Project delivery, in particular in the built environment world, is highly fragmented, as we all know. Governance remains complex in these contexts. AI adds a further complicating factor on top of an already highly fragmented and messy landscape of organisations, data, systems, decision making etc.
- Risk appetite & trust.** Government’s AI Playbook [2] insists organisations retain “meaningful human control at the right stages” and secure board-level oversight before automating high-stakes decisions. Many leadership teams respond by forcing the development of AI through the same gates as conventional ICT, elongating approvals and eroding momentum. Also given the rate of development of AI the case for investment and the technology itself will almost certainly become misaligned.
- Mis-aligned metrics.** PMI research [3] [4] across 650 firms shows success correlates not with leadership “excitement”, but with preparedness and Board involvement: companies whose Boards are “fully involved” in AI strategy are three times more likely to be implementation leaders (48 % vs 16 %). Leaders tie AI benefits to

STRATEGIC
ALIGNMENT
+
CAPABLE
PEOPLE
+
MODERN
COMMERCIAL
LEVERS

outcome-based KPIs (carbon, customer satisfaction, etc), not just headcount and effectiveness savings.

Recommended actions – leadership & alignment

1. **Name an executive AI sponsor** at main board level, supported by an enterprise AI board that spans digital, commercial and assurance and which has the accountability and power to make timely decisions.
2. **Shift from cost-saving to value-creation metrics** — and report carbon abatement, schedule certainty, social value transparently alongside financial ROI to show the value from the investment in AI.
3. **Fund the “boring plumbing”** of data platforms, machine learning operations (MLOps¹), model assurance before chasing flashy proof-of-concepts that do not have the necessary underpinning to ever allow them to be used project or enterprise wide.
4. **Embed meaningful human oversight** into stage-gate governance to maintain stakeholder and public trust while accelerating approvals.

3.2 Data Pooling & Interoperability

UK project delivery remains hampered by siloed data and bespoke systems. BIM models, cost spreadsheets and programme schedules are often stored in incompatible formats, forcing manual re-keying or custom scripts that introduce delay and risk [5].

Organisations also hesitate to pool data without a **trusted legal framework**, fearing Intellectual Property (IP) loss or privacy breaches. Although techniques like **differential privacy** could enable aggregated analytics without exposing individual records, they are rarely applied beyond research pilots [13].

Strong **data governance** and **strategic alignment** are critical to break this impasse. The Government’s **AI Playbook** explicitly mandates that teams define data ownership, quality standards and ethical controls before pursuing AI pilots [2]. A compelling example is the **National Underground Asset Register (NUAR) MVP**, which unites utility owners on a neutral platform under a clear Data Distribution Agreement and role-based access controls [13]. By demonstrating that a government-led “data trust” can secure each party’s data while enabling shared insights, NUAR provides a live blueprint for overcoming mistrust [13].

¹ MLOps, short for Machine Learning Operations, is a set of practices that aims to streamline the process of taking machine-learning models from development to production and then maintaining them.

Challenge	Mitigation
Incompatible data formats (BIM, cost, schedule)	Convene an industry working group to adopt open schemas (e.g. Industry Foundation Classes for BIM, Project Cost Information for cost data) [5]
Lack of a trusted sharing framework	Establish a neutral “data trust” with IP, liability and breach-redress rules modelled on NUAR [13]
Privacy & IP concerns	Embed Data Distribution Agreements and privacy-enhancing techniques (e.g. differential privacy) [2][13]

Recommended Actions – Data Pooling & Interoperability

- **Mandate Core Data Standards.** Require open, non-proprietary formats (IFC², PCI) in all major public contracts to ensure interoperability.
 - **Stand Up a Sector Data Trust.** Create an independent body (e.g. via the Infrastructure Client Group) to govern data-sharing rules, IP ownership, liability and breach redress, using NUAR’s MVP as a template.
- Deploy Common Data Environments.** Invest in secure, cloud-hosted platforms with role-based access and end-to-end encryption to host shared BIM, cost and schedule data for real-time collaboration.

3.3 Digital & Tech Constraints (including Legacy Tech)

A significant portion of central government and client IT is now “legacy”—obsolete, unsupported and incompatible with modern analytics. The Public Accounts Committee found that **28 percent of central government systems are impossible to update**, trapping data in silos and undermining AI ambitions [14]. This **technical debt**, compounded by **vendor lock-in**, forces teams into manual workarounds and bespoke integrations that stifle innovation [8].

Many legacy systems are monolithic and on-premises, lacking Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) or using proprietary formats that prevent real-time data exchange. Consequently, decision-makers rely on static reports rather than live insights [5]. Under-

² IFC – Industry Foundation Classes is a non-proprietary, open and neutral data format used in Building Information Modelling (BIM) for exchanging information between software applications.

investment in cloud platforms and modern data architectures exacerbates the issue: although the Government Digital Strategy 2022–2025 earmarked funds for remediation, progress has been slow, leaving a “sclerotic” digital architecture ill-suited to AI workloads [15].

Emerging technical responses—endorsed by the **Technology Code of Practice** and the **Construction Playbook**—include **cloud-native** design and **API-first** approaches:

- **Microservices & containerisation** break monoliths into modular components, each exposed via standard APIs and deployed in containers (e.g. Docker/Kubernetes) for consistency and scalability [16].
- **API wrapping layers** allow legacy applications to expose key functions via REST³ful endpoints, enabling AI tools to access data without rewriting core systems [17].
- **Incremental modernisation**, an agile strategy, delivers quick wins (e.g. migrating document management to cloud) while gradually updating and improving other existing systems so they work smoothly with the new platform[18].

Constraint	Solution
Legacy systems & technical debt	Audit high-risk systems and execute a phased remediation roadmap, prioritising unsupportable platforms [14]
Vendor lock-in & closed architectures	Mandate open, documented APIs and non-proprietary outputs (JSON, XML, IFC) in all new procurements [16][17]
Under-investment in cloud/data foundations	Secure ring-fenced funding and embed senior digital leadership to drive cloud migrations and platform refreshes [2][15]

³ REST – Representational State Transfer is an architectural style for designing networked applications, it leverages the HTTP protocol for data exchange between systems.

Recommended Actions – Digital and Tech Constraint

- **Phased Legacy Remediation.** Conduct a sector-wide audit of legacy systems; allocate ring-fenced budgets to upgrade or replace critical platforms in line with AI/data objectives.
- **Mandate Open APIs in Procurement.** Require all new systems and major upgrades to expose data and functions via standard APIs and output in open formats (JSON, XML, IFC).

Embed Digital Leadership. Appoint senior digital officers (e.g. Chief Digital Information Officers) in departments and project boards to oversee modernisation, enforce standards and align investment with AI/data goals.

3.4 Skill and culture gaps

AI is amplifying the built environment’s long-standing workforce challenges. In RICS’ 2023 digitalisation survey [5], “shortage of skilled persons” ranked as the second-highest blocker, flagged as *high* by 50 % of global respondents. FIDIC/EY [1] echoes the theme, warning that “hands-on skills and experience are still valued above digital literacy, creating a skills gap between age groups”.

Gap	Manifestation	Evidence
Technical supply	Scarcity of data scientists, MLOps and cyber specialists with domain context	CECA [6] calls for industry-specific data-ethics and security courses
AI-fluency in delivery roles	PMs and engineers lack prompt-engineering and model-interpretation skills	APM’s forthcoming BoK [7] highlights need for translators who can turn predictive insights into schedule and risk actions
Cultural resistance	Fear of job displacement; mistrust of algorithmic outputs and the risk this puts onto the individual as to its use	FIDIC/EY survey [1] reports “low appetite for change and a culture of suspicion”
Patchy CPD pathways	Professional bodies only just integrating AI into their developmental and professional standards	CECA [6] recommends “role-specific training” and formal CPD on AI risk

PMI’s cross-sector study [4] underlines that **leadership preparedness trumps enthusiasm**: 64 % of Leaders show full technical readiness versus 21 % of Followers, and “data quality

management” plus “business–technology integration” top the skill wish-list for all cohorts.

Collaboration makes a difference through the PDA Coalition

The Project Data Analytics (PDA) Coalition is a delivery-led, practitioner-run alliance of clients, suppliers and delivery teams—from Rolls-Royce to the UK Ministry of Defence—that tackles shared project-delivery problems with data and AI. Organised into domain-specific product groups (such as scheduling, risk and assurance), members jointly define pain points, co-design lightweight tools on off-the-shelf platforms, and pilot them on live projects, turning hackathon ideas into operational solutions in weeks.

By embedding apprentices inside these groups, the Coalition grows sector-ready data talent while generating tangible results—slashing statement-of-work preparation from six weeks to an hour, cutting data-quality issues by a third and producing open-source dashboards and apps that even subcontractors can adopt without costly software. In short, the PDA Coalition shows how grassroots, cross-sector collaboration can deliver scalable, low-barrier project-data innovation today, without waiting for top-down mandates.

Recommended actions - Skill and culture gaps

- Establish a **National Skills Coalition** to curate modular micro-credentials on data ethics, prompt design and AI assurance amongst other critical areas.
- Incentivise **industry secondments** between tech vendors, consultancies and project owners to cross-pollinate expertise.
- Set **minimum AI-literacy requirements** in professional chartership renewal; align with UK-Gov AI Playbook [2] Principle 5 on life-cycle competence.
- Create “**safe sandboxes**” where teams can experiment with LLMs on synthetic datasets to build confidence and capability before live deployment.

3.5 Procurement & commercial models

Current procurement practice still rewards lowest capital price, not digital value. Three inter-locking issues dominate:

1. **Outcome blindness.** Transactional contracts focus on deliverables, leaving no budget line for data pipelines, model retraining or cloud inference costs. FIDIC/EY [1] argues that “transactional contracts with the supply chain that limit data sharing are slowing adoption”.

2. **IP & liability grey zones.** CIOB [8] flags copyright, confidentiality and generative-AI hallucination risk as new dispute grounds under standard NEC/JCT forms. The Playbook’s legal annex reminds buyers to decide “which parties will own which parts of any intellectual property generated” and balance risk accordingly.
3. **Lack of AI-ready clauses and routes-to-market.** The cabinet Office’s Guidelines for AI Procurement [2] and PPN 02/24 promote transparency on supplier AI use and encourage Dynamic Purchasing Systems for an evolving supply base. Yet few project owners incorporate these tools.

Emerging practice

- **Integrated data & AI platforms** and **Data-as-a-Service models** proposed by FIDIC/EY[1] allow shared savings and monetisation of curated data sets across stakeholders.
- Contractors such as Gleeds [12] now **embed AI tools (bid-writer, compliance bots) into baseline fee proposals**, proving digital value can be priced from day one.

Recommended actions - Procurement & commercial models

1. **Adopt outcome-based procurement** – link supplier reward to whole-life net-zero, safety or cost-certainty outcomes measured via AI dashboards.
2. Publish an “**AI Schedule of Amendments**” for the main forms of contract including NEC, FIDIC and JCT, covering:
 - shared data-pool obligations;
 - model drift & update protocols;
 - AI bias/ethics assurance;
 - IP ownership of fine-tuned models.
3. Leverage **CCS AI Marketplace and DPS frameworks** [2] to accelerate compliant sourcing whilst avoiding vendor lock-in.
4. Pilot **shared-savings risk-reward mechanisms** where clients co-fund AI infrastructure and share downstream efficiency gains.

3.6 Risk, ethics and assurance

As artificial intelligence becomes increasingly embedded in the design, delivery, and evaluation of major infrastructure projects, robust risk management, ethical oversight, and transparent assurance are no longer optional—they are foundational. Without public trust, clear regulatory alignment, or demonstrable accountability, AI-enabled systems risk not only rejection or misuse but also systemic failure in safety-critical environments.

The built environment presents a particularly complex context for AI assurance. Project delivery involves long asset lifecycles, multi-actor supply chains, evolving data sources, and significant public impact. AI introduces new risks—ranging from algorithmic bias in prioritisation models to explainability gaps in predictive maintenance or scheduling tools. Ensuring that these risks are managed responsibly is essential for safe, effective, and trusted deployment.

Recent UK guidance from the AI Safety Institute, Alan Turing Institute, DSIT, and HM Treasury has provided a stronger foundation for AI assurance. However, implementation within infrastructure programmes remains uneven and fragmented. The following issues and emerging practices highlight what must be addressed to ensure assurance keeps pace with adoption:

Fragmented governance and unclear accountability

AI systems often operate across boundaries—between departments, delivery partners, and technology suppliers. Without clearly assigned roles and responsibilities for data, models, and outcomes, it becomes difficult to allocate accountability when things go wrong. This challenge is amplified in multi-supplier environments typical of major projects.

Absence of embedded ethical processes

The Alan Turing Institute has consistently found that many organisations treat ethics as a compliance checkbox rather than a core part of development. This leads to reactive, inconsistent consideration of fairness, bias, transparency, and public acceptability.

Lack of structured assurance mechanisms

While high-risk sectors like transport and defence have long used safety cases, few infrastructure programmes have adopted structured, auditable assurance approaches for AI. The result is a gap in trust and traceability, particularly where models influence decisions with long-term impact.

Innovation bottlenecks through over-regulation

Overly cautious, one-size-fits-all assurance processes risk stifling innovation. As DSIT and the AI Safety Institute note, assurance should be proportionate to risk. Treating all AI tools as if they pose frontier-level danger will delay adoption without improving safety.

Insufficient use of guidance from Green, Magenta and Teal Books

The Green Book (HM Treasury, 2024b) now incorporates wider value considerations—including net zero, place-based equity, and long-term impact—which AI systems must align with in their design and appraisal. The Magenta Book (HM Treasury, 2024a) includes annexes on evaluating AI-enabled interventions, reinforcing the need for robust monitoring, evaluation, and adaptive learning. The Teal Book (HM Treasury, 2025) specifically addresses delivery in complex environments, recommending assurance practices suited to long-duration, high-stakes programmes.

A variety of new practices are now emerging in response to these challenges:

Ethics-by-design and process-based governance

The Alan Turing Institute’s ethics workbooks and TEA (Transparency, Ethics and Accountability) platform are now being used to embed ethical reflection throughout the AI lifecycle. This includes early identification of ethical risks, structured stakeholder engagement, and defined accountability structures.

Modular AI safety cases

The AI Safety Institute is advancing the use of structured “AI safety cases” that document model purpose, assumptions, testing, risks, and governance decisions—mirroring long-standing engineering safety assurance models.

Independent audits and cross-functional review boards

Emerging practice across the public and private sectors includes third-party audits of algorithm performance and fairness, as well as programme-level AI ethics and assurance boards. These boards bring together legal, technical, user, and social impact expertise.

Transparency and model documentation

Tools such as “model cards” and system documentation templates—endorsed by the Alan Turing Institute and others—are being trialled in large-scale digital programmes. These provide a standardised way of communicating how AI systems work, what data they rely on, and how risks are being mitigated.

Proportionate assurance thresholds

DSIT and the AI Safety Institute both advocate for risk-based thresholds. Not all AI systems require the same level of oversight. Emerging frameworks enable lighter governance for low-impact tools (e.g. internal chatbots), and stricter controls for higher-risk systems (e.g. automated scheduling or asset prioritisation).

Recommended actions - Risk, ethics and assurance

1. **Establish AI Ethics & Assurance Boards:** Set up AI Ethics and Assurance Boards for all major programs with cross-functional expertise.
2. **Mandate AI Safety Cases:** Require AI safety cases for models that influence program decisions, using templates from the AI Safety Institute.
3. **Integrate Ethics-by-Design:** Embed ethics-by-design into project governance using the Alan Turing Institute's workbooks and TEA framework.
4. **Apply Assurance Thresholds:** Use proportionate assurance thresholds to differentiate between low- and high-risk systems based on DSIT's guidance.
5. **Align with Guidance:** Ensure AI tools follow Green, Magenta, and Teal Book guidance, considering long-term value, equity, carbon impact, and adaptive learning.
6. **Commission Independent Audits:** Conduct and publish key findings of independent audits for high-risk AI tools to enhance public trust.

Implementation Framework

To move from theory to tangible delivery, this section sets out a structured implementation framework designed to address the systemic barriers outlined in Section 3. Each barrier area is addressed using a common structure:

- Target State
- 90-Day Starter Actions
- 12-Month Milestones
- Success Metrics

Barrier	Target State	90-Day Actions	12-Month Milestones	Success Metrics
Leadership & Alignment	Clear executive sponsorship of AI and data strategy, with governance embedded across delivery, commercial and assurance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appoint an AI sponsor; • establish a cross-functional AI board; • align executive scorecards with AI-enabled outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence of AI embedded into stage gate governance; • at least one pilot programme showing measurable delivery benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of major programmes with executive AI sponsor; time to approval for AI-enabled proposals; satisfaction with AI use in decision-making.
Data Pooling & Inter-operability	Trusted frameworks for data sharing, common standards, and interoperable platforms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign Data Distribution Agreements for active projects; • define minimum data schema; • designate programme data stewards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared CDE in use across supply chain; common data standards adopted by top-tier suppliers • Mandated Data Distribution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of suppliers using common formats; number of projects using shared data environments; data quality scores.

Barrier	Target State	90-Day Actions	12-Month Milestones	Success Metrics
			Agreements across all new projects	
Digital & Tech Constraints	Cloud-native, modular architecture with APIs for legacy access and future scalability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audit legacy systems; • wrap high-priority systems with APIs; • secure funding for digital upgrades. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Migration of 25% of legacy systems to cloud-native equivalents; • API access live for top 5 critical data sources. 	% legacy systems with API access; % of spend aligned to digital foundations; cloud usage stats.
Skill and Culture Gaps	AI-literate project professionals supported by modular, accredited CPD and sandbox testing environments.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch industry AI skills coalition; • define baseline AI literacy levels per role; • publish training roadmap. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1,000 professionals trained in AI literacy; • first cross-sector secondments delivered. 	Training uptake rates; staff confidence in using AI; skill-readiness ratings.
Procurement & Commercial Models	Outcome-based contracts with AI-ready clauses and shared-savings models.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draft AI Schedule of Amendments for NEC/FIDIC; • revise tender templates to include AI use plans. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least three pilots using shared-savings model; • AI clauses embedded in central procurement templates. 	% tenders with AI clauses; number of outcome-based contracts; value of savings shared.
Risk, Ethics & Assurance	Proportionate assurance framework with AI ethics embedded into project lifecycle.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish ethics and assurance boards; • mandate safety case templates for new AI tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All major projects with AI safety case; • first independent audit published. 	% projects with active assurance board; audit pass rate; public trust indicators.

Roadmap and Roles

05

A phased implementation roadmap is required to deliver this framework effectively and at scale.

0–6 Months: Foundations and Pilots	6–18 Months: Scaling and Institutionalisation	18+ Months: Optimisation and Continuous Improvement
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surface the real and perceived business risks at a board level (Owners: Business Organisations) • Appoint executive sponsors and launch AI Boards (Owners: Departments) • Sign Data Distribution Agreements on pilot projects (Owners: Clients) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extend data standards to full portfolio; mandate use in contracts (Owners: Cabinet Office, CCS) • Deploy AI pilots with structured safety cases and external audits (Owners: Programme Directors) • Embed AI clauses in all new framework procurements (Owners: CCS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate AI performance into Green/Magenta/Teal Book reviews (Owners: HM Treasury) • Refresh CPD standards to reflect AI-readiness (Owners: Professional Bodies) • Publish model cards and test results for transparency (Owners: Suppliers, Regulators)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish National Skills Coalition (Owners: DSIT, Industry Bodies) • Wrap APIs around top 5 legacy systems (Owners: Delivery Bodies) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct mid-point review and update metrics (Owners: NISTA, DSIT) 	
--	---	--

The roadmap will require coordination across Government Departments, delivery agencies, suppliers, regulators and professional bodies. Ownership must be clearly defined per milestone to drive accountability and momentum.

The recommendations set out in this framework are not optional add-ons. They are core enablers of effective, ethical and scalable AI adoption in the built environment.

Next steps include piloting the framework with flagship government programmes and iterating based on

feedback and impact. A central capability hub, supported by NISTA, should provide ongoing support to departments and suppliers alike.

By working in partnership—and focusing on interoperability, capability, and trust—we can unlock the full potential of AI and data to deliver better outcomes for citizens, faster and more reliably than ever before.

Policy Levers and Recommendations

To enable adoption at pace and scale, strategic interventions are needed from central Government, regulators, and cross-sector coordination bodies. The following policy levers are recommended:

Department	Policy Lever
HM Treasury	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Update investment guidance to require AI-readiness and digital maturity assessments in Green Book business cases. • Embed AI and data use cases within Teal Book complexity management scenarios. • Allocate ring-fenced funding in Spending Reviews for public sector AI pilots and assurance capability.
DSIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand AI Opportunities Plan with delivery-focused implementation pathways. • Fund the scaling of trusted data environments and national AI infrastructure (e.g., compute, sandboxes, testbeds). • Sponsor professional standards and open-source tools to support safe AI deployment.
Regulators and NISTA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandate use of AI Safety Case templates for critical systems. • Endorse assurance thresholds based on system risk level, aligned with Magenta Book principles. • Facilitate co-regulation forums between industry, suppliers, and government bodies to support adaptive governance.
Cross-government Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Align procurement reform efforts (CCS, Cabinet Office) with AI-enabling contract templates. • Expand the IPA Project Delivery Data Strategy and Functional Standards to explicitly reference AI. • Create shared accountability frameworks for cross-departmental AI-enabled project delivery.

Practitioner

07

Toolkit (Annex)

To support day-one adoption, the following practical tools and resources are recommended:

Tool	Description
AI Implementation Readiness Checklist	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Is there a nominated AI sponsor with cross-functional support?• Have AI use cases been mapped to delivery outcomes?• Are assurance thresholds defined by system risk?• Has baseline training been delivered to delivery teams?• Is an ethics review process in place?
Standardised Data Sharing Agreement Template	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Defines access rights, IP boundaries, and security measures.• Aligns with NUAR principles and national data standards.• Supports integration with BIM and geospatial datasets.
Metrics and KPIs for AI-Enabled Project Delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Outcome impact (e.g., time/cost/scope variance improvement).• Operational metrics (e.g., number of AI use cases deployed, model reuse rate).• Trust and safety (e.g., number of safety cases submitted, audit pass rate, stakeholder confidence).

This toolkit should be centrally maintained and updated by a national coordination body such as NISTA, with feedback loops from programme teams to inform iteration and continuous improvement.

Case Studies

08

Case Study: DataForm Lab Platform – A Data-Driven Framework for Seamless Offsite Construction Delivery

DataForm Lab’s platform provides a compelling case for the practical application of AI and data infrastructure in the built environment, offering a fully integrated digital workflow from project inception through to factory production and supply chain coordination. By embedding data at the core of its architecture, the platform addresses long-standing fragmentation in project delivery and exemplifies how theoretical benefits can be realised in practice.

The platform begins by ingesting project design data, which is automatically configured into manufacturable building products - such as wall, floor, and ceiling cassettes. This transformation is enabled by a digitised knowledge base that embeds manufacturer-specific design and production rules, material and procurement constraints, and onsite assembly logic. The result is a seamless translation from architectural intent to production-ready outputs, including machine code and bill of materials.

Crucially, the platform also incorporates advanced optimisation algorithms that use project-specific design complexity to drive factory scheduling and resource allocation. This enables dynamic production sequencing and adaptive factory planning, improving throughput and responsiveness, even as project inputs evolve.

Information is hosted in a cloud-based environment, ensuring real-time accessibility across all stakeholders. There is no reliance on static file exchanges anymore; instead, a continuous data flow ensures consistency and eliminates version control issues.

The platform also maintains a robust “golden thread” of data. Descriptive analytics provide a full audit trail of what occurred, when, and by whom; while diagnostic analytics reveal why decisions were made and under what conditions. This level of transparency and traceability supports accountable, efficient, and data-driven project delivery - demonstrating a scalable model for implementing AI and data in construction.

Case Study: The National Underground Asset Register

The National Underground Asset Register (NUAR) provides a compelling case for applied geospatial data. It offers a unified digital map of buried pipes, cables, and ducts across England, Wales, and Northern Ireland.

NUAR overcomes the chronic fragmentation of asset records held by over 650 public- and private-sector owners by embedding interoperable data standards at its core. This enables shared location intelligence to translate into tangible safety and efficiency gains for street works.

The service begins by automatically ingesting legacy utility plans in CAD, GIS, and PDF formats. These plans are then transformed into a harmonised feature schema defined by the Geospatial Commission's data model. A digitised knowledge base encodes asset-owner metadata, positional tolerances, and attribute rules, turning historical drawings into accurate, searchable layers within the register.

The consolidated dataset exposes geometry, material, and status attributes to field engineers and third-party systems through secure APIs. Advanced spatial analytics and machine-learning routines enrich the map, interpolating missing depths, flagging potential clashes, and ranking excavation risk based on historic strike data. These insights drive dynamic planning tools that coordinate multi-utility works and street-clearing permits, reducing unnecessary excavations and associated works.

NUAR replaces ad-hoc requests with a secure, proximity-based access model: users can only retrieve data within each asset owner's defined service area and under legally enforceable Data Ingestion and Distribution Agreements. Asset owners and their approved contractors push datasets automatically via standardised APIs, delivering consistent geospatial and textual asset information without manual intervention. Robust role-based permissions and immutable audit logs record every view and edit, ensuring transparent, traceable access while safeguarding sensitive assets.

All information is hosted in a cloud-based environment on UK-sovereign infrastructure, delivering real-time browser and mobile access. Robust role-based access controls protect sensitive networks, while immutable audit logs maintain a transparent chain of who viewed or edited each asset layer and when. Descriptive dashboards evidence what works occurred, while diagnostic views explain why.

NUAR thus offers a scalable model for data-driven infrastructure management. It has the potential to avert many of the 60,000 accidental utility strikes that currently blight UK works each year.

References

1. **EY & FIDIC** (September 2024) *How Artificial Intelligence Can Unlock a New Future for Infrastructure*. London / Geneva: Ernst & Young and the International Federation of Consulting Engineers.
2. **HM Government – Cabinet Office** (February 2025) *Artificial Intelligence Playbook for the UK Government*. London: Crown Copyright.
3. **PMI – Project Management Institute** (2025a) *Leading AI Transformation: Organisational Strategies for Project Professionals*. Newtown Square, PA: PMI.
4. **PMI – Project Management Institute** (March 2025b) *Sustainability in the Age of AI: The Integration Imperative*. Newtown Square, PA: PMI.
5. **RICS – Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors** (June 2023) *Digitalisation in Construction Report 2023 – Research*. London: RICS.
6. **CECA – Civil Engineering Contractors Association** (May 2025) *Artificial Intelligence in UK Construction*. London: CECA.
7. **APM – Association for Project Management** (2025, draft) *Body of Knowledge 8: Data Analytics and AI in Project Management*. High Wycombe: APM.
8. **CIOB – Chartered Institute of Building** (2024) *CIOB AI Playbook – Chapter “AI, the Law and Contracts”*. Ascot: CIOB.
9. **Cabinet Office – Government Commercial Function** (2024) *Guidelines for AI Procurement*.
10. **Cabinet Office – Procurement Policy Note 02/24** (2024) *Transparency in Artificial Intelligence Procurement*. London: Crown Commercial Service.
11. **Crown Commercial Service** (2025) *AI Marketplace / Dynamic Purchasing System (DPS) – framework documentation*. London: CCS.
12. **Gleeds** (October 2024) *Gleeds AI Initiatives* (internal briefing paper).
13. **Cabinet Office** (2023) **National Underground Asset Register: Minimum Viable Product (MVP)**. London: UK Government. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/nuar-minimum-viable-product-mvp/nuar-minimum-viable-product-mvp>
14. **House of Commons Public Accounts Committee** (June 2024) **Digital Unity? Follow-Up on Government Legacy Systems**. London: House of Commons. Available at: <https://committees.parliament.uk/publications/43703>
15. **Cabinet Office** (2022) **Government Digital Strategy 2022–2025**. London: Crown Copyright. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/government-digital-strategy-2022-to-2025>
16. **Cabinet Office** (2021) **Technology Code of Practice for UK Government Services**. London: Crown Copyright. Available at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/technology-code-of-practice/technology-code-of-practice>

17. Cabinet Office (October 2020) **The Construction Playbook: Government guidance for the procurement and delivery of major projects**. London: Crown Copyright. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-construction-playbook>
18. Infrastructure and Projects Authority (July 2021) **Project Delivery Roadmap 2030: Transforming Infrastructure Project Performance**. London: IPA. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/project-delivery-roadmap-2030>
19. Alan Turing Institute (2023a) **AI Ethics and Governance Workbooks**. Available at: <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/publications/ai-ethics-governance-workbooks>
20. Alan Turing Institute (2023b) **TEA: Transparency, Ethics and Accountability Framework**. Available at: <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/ai-ethics-practice>
21. Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation (CDEI) (2023) **Responsible Data Use in the Built Environment**. London: CDEI.
22. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) (2024a) **Introduction to AI Assurance**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/introduction-to-ai-assurance>
23. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) (2024b) **AI Safety Institute: Technical Charter**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-safety-institute-charter>
24. HM Treasury (2024a) **The Magenta Book: Supplementary Annexes on Evaluating AI Interventions**. London: HM Treasury.
25. HM Treasury (2024b) **The Green Book: Appraisal and Evaluation in Central Government**. Updated edition. London: HM Treasury.
26. HM Treasury (2025) **The Teal Book: Delivering Complex Projects**. London: HM Treasury.
27. Cabinet Office (2022) GovS 002: **Project Delivery Functional Standard**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/project-delivery-functional-standard>.
28. Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport (2020) **National Data Strategy**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-national-data-strategy>.
29. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (2025) **AI Opportunities Plan**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ai-opportunities-plan>.
30. Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (2025) **AI Safety Institute renamed AI Security Institute** – press release. Available at:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/ai-safety-institute-becomes-ai-security-institute>.

31. Infrastructure and Projects Authority (2021) **Transforming Infrastructure Performance: Roadmap to 2030**. London: Cabinet Office.
32. Infrastructure and Projects Authority (2022) **Project Delivery Data Strategy**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/project-delivery-data-strategy>.
33. HM Treasury (2025) **UK Infrastructure: A 10 year Strategy**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/uk-infrastructure-a-10-year-strategy>
34. Dept for Science Innovation and Technology (2021) **National AI Strategy**. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy>

End.

<https://www.pdataskforce.com>